

Soil-free legume culture for nodule production and symbiont isolation

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Abstract. Authentication of rhizobial strains is normally conducted with contamination control, and particularly when done under biosecurity containment. Existing systems are not particularly well suited to a biosecurity context, so the purpose of this work was to develop a new system for contained, soil-free growth of legumes for nodule production and symbiont isolation where biosecurity containment is mandated. This system used autoclavable polycarbonate containers with expanded clay aggregate growth medium, which met the criteria of being fully contained, compact, low maintenance, not impacted by impure inoculum, simple and relatively quick, generating minimal waste, with all operations easily conducted in a biosafety cabinet. It was tested with chickpea, field pea, lentil and narrow-leaf lupin, producing nodules within 3 weeks suitable for contamination-free (re)isolation of rhizobia. The system proved suitable for biosecurity purposes, but also offers advantages for rhizobial authentication or rapid assessment of nodulation more widely.

Keywords: biosecurity, containment, legume, nodulation, rhizobia, soil-free

Released online 9 March 2026

Introduction

In rhizobiology, the authentication of rhizobial strains is conducted with contamination control in various plant growth systems (Yates *et al.*, 2016). In addition to authentication in the homologous host, such systems can also be used to determine host range and symbiotic effectiveness. For small-seeded legumes, the plants can be fully enclosed in sterilised containers (e.g. Petri dishes, tubes or vials) with sterilised, inert substrates (e.g., agar, sand or vermiculite) and nitrogen-free nutrient solutions. For larger-seeded legumes, the systems used (e.g., Leonard jars, polythene pouches, pots or hydroponics) mostly have the shoot of the host plant exposed and contamination control is effected by bottom watering and surface coverings with sterilised, inert materials (e.g. gravel or plastic beads). As detailed by Yates *et al.* (2016), these systems each have their merits and limitations depending on the specific context.

In the context that prompted this work, that is, biosecurity containment during the isolation and authentication of chickpea rhizobia from imported nodules, none of the systems described by Yates *et al.* (2016) or elsewhere (e.g., Jones *et al.*, 2013)

were suitable. The plants needed to be grown (1) fully-contained in a relatively small growth cabinet, (2) with establishment, watering and assessment done in a biosafety cabinet with restrictive operator access, (3) watered no more than once per week and (4) useful for inoculation with either crushed nodules that would have a mixed surface and internal microbiome and pure cultures. It was also desirable if the system was (5) simple, (6) relatively quick and (7) generated minimal waste.

For desi chickpeas with a moderate seed weight (>150 mg), none of the existing systems met the first two criteria. All the systems suitable for chickpeas had open shoot growth, could not fit conveniently (vertically) through the 160-mm high access to the biosafety cabinet and would not be space efficient in the available growth cabinet. A pouch system (Weaver and Graham, 1994) had been used previously (under prior biosecurity conditions), but with its small water volume and open shoots, watering needed to be done at least twice per week by a relatively awkward process. Also, given that this system has an internal paper support for root growth, it is prone to fungal contamination as the top of this paper is open to the air and provides a

suitable substrate for growth of cellulose-degrading fungi, so would not be suitable for an microbially-impure, crushed-nodule inoculant¹. Similarly, agar-based systems, though minimally prone to air- and seedborne contamination would not be suitable for inoculation with crushed-nodules.

This paper describes an alternative method growth of legumes for nodule production and symbiont isolation developed specifically for isolation of rhizobium, and release of strains from biosecurity containment and other applications. The method was initially developed for chickpea, being refined over multiple runs, with validation experiments then conducted on that host and three other legume species, viz. field pea, lentil and narrow-leaf lupin.

Materials and methods

Materials

Containerised host plants were grown aseptically in a soil-free system in a Sanyo Versatile Environmental Test Chamber (MLR-351, Sanyo Electric Co., Osaka, Japan) set to 21°C with a 16:8 h L:D photoperiod with 12 Osram FL40SSW/37 fluorescent tubes. The containers used were autoclavable 500-mL polycarbonate containers (90 × 125 mm) with polypropylene cap (Techno Plas Pty Ltd, St Marys, SA, Australia) with a growth substrate of about 300 mL of expanded clay aggregate (ECA). The Sanyo MLR-351 had the capacity for 140 containers with a minimum of c. 200 mm between the shelves. All preparative, maintenance and assessment tasks were done in a Gelman Sciences BH series biosafety cabinet (East Lansing, MI, USA).

The ECA used was a generic product manufactured in India, nominally 12 × 20-mm pellets but quite variable size. For initial use, the ECA was washed twice (to remove dust) then soaked overnight in cold tap water, and when reused², it was soaked twice for >1 h and then overnight in hot tap water (initially at 60°C) to remove any added nutrients. After the initial washing or overnight soaking, the ECA was drained, dispensed into each container, using a generously full 250 mL glass beaker. Twenty-five mL of nitrogen-free nutrient solution (McKnight, 1949) prepared in sterile reverse-osmosis (RO) water from

a 100× stock was added and the lid loosely fitted before autoclaving at 121°C for 30 min with 30-min slow exhaust and 20-min cooldown. The pH of the ECA surface and free liquid in the container after cooling to room temperature was c. 6.5.

General method

Test legume seeds were surface sterilised³ in 80% alcohol for 2 min, air dried in a biosafety cabinet, rinsed twice in sterile tap water and soaked overnight at 21°C in a sterile specimen contain (120 mL, with lid loosely fitted) to imbibe and commence germination with no or a low proportion radicals emerging before transferring to the growth substrate. Using sterile forceps, two imbibed seeds were placed centrally, covered with 1-2 pieces of ECA and the cap loosely refitted to the container. The containers were incubated at 21°C with an 16:8 h L:D photoperiod for 7 days before inoculating emerged seedlings

After 7 days, nearly all containers had at least one emerged chickpea seedling, and these were inoculated with suspensions of either agar cultures or crushed dried nodules. For cultures, a 10-μL loopfull of bacterial colony was suspended (by vigorous shaking) in 1-mL sterile RO water in a sterile 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube and poured directly to the base of emerged seedling(s) with the central placement of the imbibed seeds facilitating the joint inoculation of two seedlings at this step. For dried nodules, these were rehydrated (at least 2 h at room temperature or 24 h at 5°C) in 1-mL sterile tap water in a sterile 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube then crushed using sterile (flamed and cooled) 130-mm blunt-tipped stainless steel forceps. The resultant suspension was poured directly at the base of the seeding and followed with a single wash of the tube with 1-mL sterile tap water. The container (without being recapped) was covered with a 180 × 170 mm polythene bag to maintain humidity and minimise the risk of microbial contamination, and returned to the growth chamber.

The plants were then grown for 3 weeks before examining the root system for nodules. Water was added 2 and 3 weeks after sowing as needed. The initial free-water depth was c. 15 mm and this was replenished with a 25 mL addition, or less if free water was still evident in the bottom of the container. Water was added with an Eppendorf

¹ Under biosecurity containment any unit with evident microbial contamination would need to appropriately discarded.

² Reused (recycled) substrate was not experimentally compared with new substrate, but through repeated reuse there was no indication of impact on plant growth, so the washing protocol was found to be effective.

³ This treatment is less aggressive than normally used for seed surface sterilisation, but in this system main goal was to decontaminate for rhizobia, and it was effective for this purpose with no nodulation occurring in the controls.

Varispenser 2.5-25 mL bottle-top dispenser on a 2 L Schott bottle in the biosafety cabinet. This cabinet has a 160-mm opening with glass shield in operating position, so the containers with plastic covers could be transferred into the cabinet held vertically without dislodging the substrate or damaging the plants (including when the plant had grown well above the rim of the container). The spout of the Eppendorf dispenser on the 2-L bottle was about 230 mm above the bench which allowed direct addition of water to the container by lifting the polythene bag to expose only c. 20% of the mouth of the container and keeping the plants shoots fully within the bag (thus minimising the risk of contamination).

Three to 4 weeks after sowing the root systems were examined for nodules. Holding the plant shoots in one hand, the contents of the container was tipped into a glass Petri dish (200 mm) to retain the ECA. With a few rapid shakes while holding the shoot, nearly all the EVA fell from the root system with the remaining few pellets easily dislodged, for example with sterile forceps, if needed. A video of this is provided in the supplementary information.

Application and validation with chickpea

The general method, given above, was refined over about 10 runs with chickpea rhizobial cultures and dried nodules, and then validated in a single experiment as follows. Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* cv. PBA Striker) seed (c. 160 mg/seed) was used and inoculated with cultures of the Australian commercial inoculant strain, *Mesorhizobium ciceri* CC1192. The inoculant was harvested from four 7-day-old cultures (yeast mannitol agar plates) by addition of 3 × 5 mL sterile RO water, and suspending with a sterile plastic spreader, combining to give a densely cloudy suspension of about 50 mL. The experiment included plants inoculated 6 and 12 days after sowing, and harvested after 3 and 4 weeks with 10 replicate containers used for each of the four treatment combinations. Inoculation (1 mL per container) was done on the same day with plants having staggered sowing dates. Ten containers from each sowing date were maintained as uninoculated controls and harvested after 4 weeks. At harvest, the number and fresh weight of nodules was recorded.

Comparison of chickpea with other legumes

For comparison with chickpea, and for validation of the method with other legumes, an experiment was conducted with chickpea (cv. PBA Striker), field pea (*Pisum sativum* cv. PBA Oura), lentil (*Vicia lens* cv. PBA Herald XT) and narrow-leaf lupin (*Lupinus*

angustifolius cv. Mandelup) inoculating with compatible cultures: CC1192 for chickpea, *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bv. *viciae*, WSM4634 for field pea and lentil, and *Bradyrhizobium lupini* WU425 for lupin. The inoculant suspensions were prepared as described above, except growth from two 14-day-old cultures for the slow-growing WU425 were suspended (c. 30 mL total) and 2 mL of added per container. Plants were grown for 5 weeks until harvest to allow more time for development of N deficiency symptoms in the controls. There were 10 inoculated and five uninoculated containers for each legume species. For chickpea and field pea the weekly watering was about 15-25 mL but for lentil and lupin it was about 10-15 and 0-10 mL, respectively, as the latter two used considerably less water. Again at harvest, number and fresh weight of nodules were recorded.

Results

For chickpea, the germination rate of the seed batch used was high with the establishment failure rate <2% with two seeds per container. The plants grew well and nodulated under the growth conditions within the 3 weeks after inoculation. The covers effectively maintained high humidity, and the foliage and roots stayed healthy in the established plants with no evidence of rot or fungal growth. The roots remained white and ramified sufficiently throughout the substrate to have sufficient roots protected from light, with ample root hairs, to allow rhizobial infection. No nodules formed in uninoculated controls. In the infrequent case of failed establishment, root rot and/or fungal development on the ungerminated seeds was sometimes evident, most likely due to pre-existing seed damage or infection not resolved by surface sterilisation of the seed.

Fig. 1 shows the growth (system and progress) from sowing to harvest of nodulated roots and Fig. 2a the nodule number and weight in the validation experiment for chickpea inoculated 6 and 10 days after sowing and harvested 3 and 4 weeks later. Delayed harvest increased nodule number (3.4 vs 5.4; $p = 0.018$) and weight (20 vs 61 mg; $p < 0.01$), but there was no direct effect of inoculation day nor any interaction between these factors for either measure. With the later harvest, slight yellowing of some uninoculated control (and unnodulated) plants was evident, but this was not definitive. In earlier runs (data not included), when grown for an additional 1 to 2 weeks yellowing was more evident but by this time, even though the nodules were larger, some of these were turning green at the proximal end and there appeared to be no additional

Fig. 1. Soil-free growth system with chickpea from sowing through to nodule harvest. A, Two imbibed chickpea seeds sown in a shallow recess in the expanded clay aggregate (ECA) used as the soilless growth substrate; B, seeds covered with one layer of ECA pellets immediately after sowing; C, chickpea seedling emergence 1 week after sowing when inoculated; D plant growth under plastic cover 4 weeks after sowing just before harvest; E, root development at harvest; and F, nodules at harvest.

benefit for ease/efficiency of isolation from these older nodules. In either case (data not included), nodules were first frozen and thawed as needed for

isolation with negligible contamination following brief surface sterilisation in 80% ethanol.

Fig. 3 shows the growth of the four legume species for representative inoculated and control plants at harvest in the comparative experiment. Shoot growth was greatest in field pea followed, in order, by chickpea, narrow-leaf lupin and lentil, but root development in narrow-leaf lupin was markedly inferior to the other three species. Although the lupin roots did not develop well below the standing water surface and turned brown, there was strong root-hair development above that level (within the dark zone of the growth substrate). Chlorosis was most evident in the controls for field pea and lentil, only just evident in chickpea but not evident in narrow-leaf lupin. In the latter case this was probably due to seed nitrogen being sufficient given the slow growth of lupin in this system. Fig 2b shows the data for nodule number and weight in the comparative experiment. Across the legume species, mean nodule number ranged from 3.5 in chickpea to 5.8 in lentil but given the variability in this measure there was no significant effect of species. However, mean nodule weight in chickpea (18 mg) and narrow-leaf lupin (23 mg) were well below that in field pea (66 mg) and lentil (57 mg) with strong significance between these two groups ($p < 0.01$). The supplementary information provided includes photographs of the progress of growth of field pea, lentil and narrow-leaf lupin in this system in a preliminary experiment (Figs S1-3), and observations on root and shoot growth and watering of four species in the comparative experiment legumes (Table S1).

Discussion

The soil-free legume culture method evaluated in this work proved practical and effective for the production of nodules and isolation of rhizobia within the context of biosecurity containment, and its use has facilitated the release of strains for further evaluation. It adequately met the criteria given above, that is in brief, fully contained, compact, low maintenance, not impacted by impure inoculum, simple and relatively quick, generating minimal waste (with even the substrate able to be reused).

A key feature of this method is the use of ECA as a soil-free growth medium as it provided suitable water retention and aeration for root growth and nodule development in a containerised system, as well as the advantage of reusability minimising waste needing regulated disposal. The earliest uses of ECA in legume research appears to be in a greenhouse study of *Acacia* rhizobia (Catt, 1985); in

Fig. 2. Nodule number (A) and nodule weight (C) for chickpea inoculated 6 and 10 days after planting and harvested 21 and 28 days after inoculation in soil-free culture with expanded clay aggregate as the substrate, and the same measures (B, C) for four legume species (chickpea, field peas, lentil and narrow-leaf lupin) inoculated 7 days after planting and harvested 35 days after inoculation under the same cultural conditions.

growth cabinets studies of enzymology of *Glycine max* and *Pisum sativum* nodules (Christensen and Jochimsen, 1983), and nitrogen fixation in *Pisum sativum* (Bertelsen, 1985); and in monoxenic culture of *Phaseolus vulgaris* for rhizobia population genetics (Young, 1985). None of these earlier reports explained the reasoning behind their choice of ECA nor the size of the ECA used. However, more recently Abd Ghani *et al.* (2023) detailed the merits of ECA for soil-free greenhouse culture of *Glycine max*, but again no aggregate size information was provided. Although most commonly in recent legume research, ECA of 2 to 4

mm, with or without vermiculite, has been used (e.g., Vittozzi *et al.*, 2021, Abel *et al.*, 2024), which is much smaller than the 12 × 20-mm pellets used in the present work. This larger size facilitated easy and rapid separation of the ECA from the roots (without sieving and/or washing, with only a small roots entering cracks in a few ECA granules) allowing all nodules to be counted and collected; again a key advantage under biosecurity containment as it can be done in a biosafety cabinet.

The system worked effectively for the four pulse species tested, although lupin was less suited to this system than the other three species. Narrow-leaf

Fig. 3. Representative uninoculated and inoculated (nodulated) plants of four legume species (A, chickpea; B, field peas; C, lentil; and D, narrow-leaf lupin) at harvest 35 days after inoculation in soil-free culture with expanded clay aggregate as the substrate.

lupin produced a moderately restricted root system of short, somewhat thickened, roots that did not extend into the free water at the base of the container or to the light-exposed sides of the container, and consequently used less water. Although few fine roots developed in lupin, there was strong development of root hairs and the nodulation was equivalent to chickpea. In contrast, field pea grew particularly well with a strongly-developed root system, developing clear symptoms of N deficiency within 4 weeks when uninoculated. This work only assessed one cultivar of each species, so it is possible that a more suitable lupin cultivar or species could be found for working with *B. lupini*, such as *Lupinus luteus* or *L. mubalis*, which are more tolerant of high soil water content (Wolko *et al.*, 2011). Likewise, the system is likely to be suitable for smaller-seeded pasture species, but might not be suitable for larger-seeded pulses such

as *Lupinus albus* or *Vicia faba* due to the size constraints of the system and greater seed-nitrogen supply.

Although there were some gains in nodule number and weight by extending the post-inoculation period from 3 to 4 weeks, this was of limited value as all inoculated plants developed nodules suitable for isolation within 3 weeks. Based on what was obtained after 3 weeks, it is possible that even after 2 weeks useable nodules could have been harvested but this was not evaluated. In this way, the system has its merits for rapid assessment of nodulation or nodule collection, but it is not likely to be useful for studies requiring plant biomass comparisons, which would be more effectively done in a soil-like growth medium, larger containers and a greenhouse. Also, nodulation can only be assessed by destructive harvest unlike a plastic pouch or glass tube system (Weaver and Graham, 1994)

In summary, the proposed system provides some clear, even essential, advantages over existing systems when working under biosecurity containment. However, for other contexts where rhizobial authentication or rapid assessment of nodulation is needed, this system has some possible advantages that suit it for consideration.

Acknowledgements

Genevieve G Hodge is thanked for her technical support during the conduct of this research, in particular the isolation of rhizobia from harvested nodules.

Funding

Funding of this work was provided by the Grains Research and Development Corporation (project UOA2312-008RTX).

Supplementary information

Supplementary video, figures, tables, data and analysis are available for download at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18856242>.

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Revision history

Ver. 002-01 - initial release

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